

Thiazoles VII-Bromination and Nitration of 2-Chlorothiazoles

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2-Chloro-4-aryl substituted thiazoles¹ on bromination and nitration yield the corresponding 5-bromo and 5-nitro thiazole derivatives respectively.

In a study of the bromination of 2-Chloro-4-aryl substituted thiazoles¹ (I), it has been found that (I) on bromination with equivalent amounts of bromine furnished products contaminated with unreacted thiazole. By using 1.2 times the equivalent quantity of bromine in presence of pyridine the 5-bromo thiazoles (II) were obtained in pure form and optimum yields.

That the bromine had entered the 5-position of the thiazole ring was confirmed by the undepressed mixed melting points of the brominated products with corresponding 2-Chloro-5-bromo thiazoles² prepared by an alternative route.

The nitration of 2-Chlorothiazoles (I) was accomplished by heating them in a nitrating mixture of acetic acid and nitric acid (d 1.42) at 80° for 7-45 minutes, depending upon the 2-Chlorothiazole used and it was found that 2-Chloro-4 (*p* methyl phenyl) thiazole required only 5-7 minutes for the nitration while 2-Chloro-4-phenyl thiazole needed longer time. By this process together with the nitro thiazoles, carboxylic acids (IV) corresponding to the group present at the 4-position of the thiazoles were also obtained. These acids are obviously formed by the oxidation of the thiazole ring. If heating time is reduced to avoid oxidation of the thiazole ring, then a mixture of nitro and unreacted thiazole was obtained which was however, separated by treating the mixture first with hot dilute ethanol and finally with a small amount of 96 per cent cold ethanol which dissolved most of the

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unreacted thiazole and the pure nitrated products were obtained by crystallisation. The analytical data of the nitrated products corresponded with mono-nitrothiazoles. The nitrothiazole obtained by the nitration of thiazole (I) (R=Cl) on oxidation with chromic acid or hydrogen peroxide furnished *p*-chloro benzoic acid (IV) (R=Cl) indicating that the nitro group does not enter the phenyl nucleus of the thiazole.

EXPERIMENTAL

Bromination of 2-Chloro-4-(p-methyl) phenyl-thiazole (I) (R=CH₃): A solution of bromine (1.9 g.) in chloroform (7 ml.) was added gradually with constant stirring to a solution of the above thiazole (2.1 g.) in chloroform (20 ml.) and pyridine (0.8 g.) during 10 minutes. Chloroform was then distilled off and the residue treated with water to dissolve out pyridine hydrobromide. The insoluble product was collected by suction and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 64°, yield 66%. The compound was confirmed to be 2-Chloro-4-(*p*-methyl)-phenyl-5-bromo-thiazole by its undepressed mixed melting point with 2-Chloro-4-(*p*-methyl) phenyl-5-bromo-thiazole².

All the remaining 2-Chlorothiazoles were brominated in the same way as above and furnished the corresponding 5-bromo derivatives in each case (Table I). 2-Chloro-4-phenyl-5-bromo-thiazole obtained by bromination of 2-Chloro-4-phenyl thiazole was a liquid. It was extracted with ether, dried over sodium sulphate and distilled under reduced pressure.

TABLE I

Sl. No.	Chlorothiazole used for bromination	Product formed	Yield %	m.p. °C	Mixed m.p. with the authentic sample
1.	2-Chloro-4-phenylthiazole.	H	71	155/7	same b.p. as that of authentic sample
2.	2-Chloro-4-(<i>p</i> -methyl) phenylthiazole.	CH ₃	66	64	64
3.	2-Chloro-(<i>p</i> -methoxy) phenylthiazole.	OCH ₃	67	96	96
4.	2-Chloro-(<i>p</i> -chloro) phenylthiazole.	Cl	68	85	85
5.	2-Chloro-4-(<i>p</i> -bromo) phenylthiazole.	Br	71	108	108

Nitration of 2-Chloro-4-phenyl-thiazole I (R=H): 2-Chloro-4-phenyl thiazole (1.0 g.) was added to a mixture of glacial acetic acid (2 ml.) and nitric acid (4 ml.) (d, 1.42) and heated on a water bath at 80° with constant stirring for 45 minutes. The reaction mixture was then poured in water and cooled in ice bath with titration. The solid product was collected by suction, basified with sodium carbonate solution, filtered, washed with water and crystallised as white needles from ethanol, m.p. 134-35°; yield 51%. (Found: C, 44.74; H, 1.84; C₉H₅N₂SO₂Cl requires C, 44.90; H, 2.08%).

The basic filtrate from above on acidification with hydrochloric acid gave benzoic acid, m.p. 121° as confirmed by its undepressed mixed melting point, with the authentic sample.

Nitration of 2-Chloro-4-(p-methyl)-phenyl-thiazole I (R=CH₃): 2-Chloro-4-(*p*-methyl)-phenyl thiazole (1.0 g.) was added to a mixture of glacial acetic acid (2 ml.) and nitric acid

(4 ml.) (d, 1.42) and heated on a water bath at 80° with constant stirring. Thiazole at first dissolved and after about 5-7 minutes the clear transparent solution became opaque. The reaction mixture was removed from the water bath and stirred vigorously. When the temperature fell below 70°, a yellow compound separated out. It was heated again on the water bath for 2-3 minutes, allowed to cool to room temperature, and diluted with water (15 ml.). The solid thus obtained was collected, basified with sodium carbonate solution and filtered. It was at first washed with hot dilute alcohol and finally with a small amount of 95% cold ethanol which removed any unreacted thiazole. The solid obtained from filtrate was found to be unreacted thiazole as confirmed through its undepressed mixed melting point with authentic sample. 2-Chloro-4-(*p*-methyl)-phenyl-5-nitro-thiazole crystallised from ethanol in yellow shining needles, m.p. 105°; yield, 57% (Found: N, 10.70; S, 12.30; $C_{10}H_7N_2SO_2Cl$, requires N, 11.02; S, 12.59%).

The basic filtrate from the above on acidification with hydrochloric acid, furnished toluic acid as confirmed by its m.p. 175°, and by its undepressed mixed melting point with the authentic sample.

Nitration of 2-Chloro-4-(p-chloro) phenylthiazole I (R=Cl): It was nitrated in the same way as 2-Chloro-4-(*p*-methyl)-phenyl thiazole except that the heating time was increased to 10-15 min. 2-Chloro-4-(*p*-chloro)-phenyl-5-nitro thiazole crystallised from ethanol in golden yellow shining needles, m.p. 110°; yield 55%. (Found: N, 10.14; S, 11.78; $C_9H_4N_2SO_2Cl$ requires N, 10.18; S, 11.64%).

The basic filtrate on acidification furnished *p*-Chloro benzoic acid, m.p. 236° confirmed by its undepressed mixed melting point with the authentic sample.

Nitration of 2-Chloro-4-(p-bromo)-phenylthiazole I (R=Br): It was nitrated in the same way as 2-Chloro-4-(*p*-chloro)-phenyl thiazole. 2-Chloro-4-(*p*-bromo) phenyl-5-nitro thiazole crystallised from ethanol in yellow shining needles, m.p. 102°; yield 59%. (Found: N, 8.76; S, 10.22; $C_9H_4N_2SO_2Cl Br$ requires N, 8.76; H, 10.01%).

The basic filtrate on acidification furnished *p*-bromo benzoic acid, m.p. 251-53° confirmed by its undepressed mixed melting point with the authentic sample.

Oxidation of nitro-thiazole obtained by the nitration of 2-Chloro-4-(p-chloro) phenyl thiazole: (i) *With chromic acid:* To a solution of nitro thiazole (2.7 g.) in acetic acid (25 ml.) was added the solution of chromium oxide (4 g.) in water (10 ml.) and it was refluxed on a sand bath for an hour and a half. Acetic acid was distilled off in vacuum and the residue treated with water and filtered. The solid mass was basified with sodium carbonate solution and filtered to remove suspended impurities. The filtrate was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, the white compound collected by suction and crystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 236°; yield 0.82 g. It was confirmed to be *p*-Chlorobenzoic acid by its undepressed mixed melting point with the authentic sample.

(ii) *With hydrogen peroxide:* The Nitrothiazole (2.7 g.), 30% hydrogen peroxide (4.75 ml.) and acetone (50 ml.) were refluxed on a water bath for 8 hr. Acetone was distilled off, the solid residue treated with sodium carbonate solution and filtered. The

insoluble yellow solid, crystallised from ethanol was found to be the original nitrothiazole confirmed by its undepressed mixed melting with the authentic sample.

The basic filtrate on acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid furnished a white compound. It was collected by suction and crystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 226°; yield 0.3 g. It was confirmed to be 4-Chloro benzoic acid by its undepressed mixed melting point with the authentic sample.

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